

A Comparison of Phase Retrieval Algorithms with a Remote Sensing Scenario

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Abstract—Three iterative algorithms for phase retrieval from intensity data are compared. Computer simulation provides the basis for comparing each algorithm’s performance for object recovery from noisy autocorrelations corrupted with exponential statistics. This paper justifies the use of exponential statistics with a simplified model of a remote sensing application.

correlation coefficient are the metrics of choice for the comparison.

Application Scenario

Consider an ideal, monochromatic, coherent laser imaging scenario with resulting laser speckle intensity images captured by a detector array. The detector array is often referred to as the pupil plane as this performs as a non-optical imaging system. Ref. [4] describes this scenario in detail. The model for the intensity data is

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$$I(u) = |\mathcal{F}^{\lambda z}\{f(x)\}|^2 \quad (1)$$

where $f(x) = |f(x)| \exp[i\theta(x)]$ is the illuminated field at the target and $\mathcal{F}^{\lambda z}$ is the scaled Fourier Transform representing Fraunhofer propagation [5]. The observed Intensity data is modeled as

$$I_o(u) = [I(u) + n(u)] \cdot H(u) \quad (2)$$

where the noise term, $n(u)$, is a zero mean noise such that the observed intensity (conditioned on the average photon values) has a poisson distribution with a mean equal to the intensity without photon noise. The mean intensity, observed in photon counts, is itself a random process with an exponential distribution [6]. $H(u)$, is the aperture function denoting the region where the speckle pattern is physically recorded; $H(u) = 1$ for the points within the measurement aperture and $H(u) = 0$ elsewhere. Because of target surface roughness, the phase at the target, $\theta(x)$, is modeled as uniformly distributed, $\sim U[-\pi, \pi]$, producing a random phasor sum at the detector plane [6], [7]. This scenario can be considered without atmospheric disturbance or the atmospheric turbulence is modeled as a phase screen directly over the target with a large propagation distance to the sensor. Each laser speckle image is considered statistically independent from all others. Of interest is the inverse Fourier Transform of the speckled intensity because of its relationship to the autocorrelation of the object field via the Wiener-Khinchin Theorem [6]. However, the autocorrelation is corrupted due to speckle noise, photon noise, and detector array effects. As Idell et al. pointed out [4], the expected value of the magnitude squared of the fourier transform of the intensity data is directly related to the object

1. INTRODUCTION

Phase retrieval for image recovery is critical in remote sensing applications where atmospheric turbulence and aperture size limit performance and resolution. Phase retrieval algorithms must overcome the blurring caused by the point spread function of the imaging system as well as noise associated with the atmosphere, the random nature of the light itself, and additive system noise such as readout noise. This paper compares, through computer simulation, the performance of three published phase retrieval algorithms: Fienup’s reconstruction from the modulus of the Fourier Transform [1], Schulz’s image recovery from autocorrelations [2], and Phillips’ maximum likelihood estimator based on Gaussian statistics [3]. The three reviewed algorithms are of importance to current research. Although, Phillips presented a statistical dampening criteria to aid in algorithm stopping, comparison of the phase retrieval algorithms will be computed after fixed number of iterations. Computational complexity and computation time are not considered in this study. Accuracy of recovery is of primary concern; therefore, mean squared error and the

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autocorrelation. We will call this operation the Idell function and describe the results in (3).

$$E[|\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{I_o(u)\}|^2] = b|h(w)|^2 + c[R_O(w) * |h(w)|^2] \quad (3)$$

where b and c are constants, R_O is the autocorrelation of the object intensity, and $|h(w)|^2$ is the impulse response of the detector array. Because of this result, an image of the target may be extracted from the Idell function with an appropriate algorithm and enough independent speckle realizations. All three phase retrieval algorithms considered in this paper operate on an autocorrelation of the object intensity function. Algorithm performance is directly tied to the initial guess, object constraints, and noise power. Object constraints typically involve *a priori* knowledge such as object extent (support) and nonnegativity.

Error Computation

The reviewed algorithms may produce solutions that are shifted and/or rotated 180° [2]. Because of this, registration of the recovered object with the original object should be performed before computing error metrics. This simulation used a vector-based, energy-normalized, non-circular cross correlation technique for image registration [8]. This technique is described mathematically as follows: First, the recovered image, i_2 , is scaled to the original image, i_1 , by the original image maximum value.

$$\hat{i}_2 = \frac{i_2}{\max\{i_1\}} \quad (4)$$

Next, two image projection vectors are formed by summing the rows and columns of the image (5). M and N are the vector lengths and $k \in \{1, 2\}$ denoting original or recovered image respectively. x and y denote the horizontal and vertical dimension, respectively. m and n index these horizontal and vertical dimensions.

$$i_{xk} = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} i_k(n, m) \quad , \quad i_{yk} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} i_k(n, m) \quad (5)$$

The cross-correlation, in one dimension, is formed by (6). Δ_{max} is the maximum anticipated shift in the projected direction. A similar equation is developed for the second dimension.

$$C_x(z) = \frac{\sum_{m=\Delta_{max}}^{M-\Delta_{max}-1} (i_{x2}(n) - \bar{i}) (i_{x1}(z+n) - \bar{i})}{\sigma_{x1}\sigma_{x2}} \quad (6)$$

The pixel shift that maximizes the cross-correlation is the best fit for registration. This operation is performed in both dimensions. This shift algorithm was only performed with whole

pixel shifts. Sub-pixel shift estimation can be accomplished with linear interpolation; however this was not done.

Mean Squared Error is a very good measure; however, outliers in the data may penalize the result more so than visual perception by human evaluators. For this reason, the correlation coefficient [9], $\rho_{1,2}$, was also computed to demonstrate how similar the recovered image is to the original. The correlation coefficient of original and recovered image is defined as

$$\rho_{1,2} = \frac{E[i_1 i_2] - E[i_1]E[i_2]}{\sigma_1 \sigma_2} \quad (7)$$

where $0 \leq \rho \leq +1$, because all considered cases involve positive images. Recovered images are constrained to be positive. If $\rho = 0$, the two images are uncorrelated. If $\rho = 1$, the two images are linearly related and exactly correlated.

2. EXPONENTIAL STATISTICS

Of interest to this study are the statistics of the Idell function, the magnitude squared of the inverse Fourier Transform of the intensity data. The statistical properties of this data were explored via computer simulation. 1,000 (128x128) laser speckle images were produced via monte-carlo simulation of the uniformly distributed random phase at the target followed by Fraunhofer propagation to the detection array. The resulting intensity images plus independent poisson noise realizations were subject to the Idell function for analysis. Figure 1 provides an example histogram for a single image pixel. All of the image pixels exhibit similar histograms. Calculating the mean and standard deviation for all of the data points, a ratio can be formed. The ratio is very nearly one for every pixel. Over 128^2 pixels, the average mean to standard deviation ratio was 1.0058. From this basic analysis, it can be concluded the processed data has an exponential distribution.

Figure 1. Histogram of single data point (1000 realizations)

This analysis is for a single frame of processed laser speckle. Replacing the expected value operator in Equation 3 with the

time average yields (8).

$$E[|\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{I_o(u)\}|^2] = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} N^{-1} \sum_{n=1}^N |\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{I_o(u)\}|^2 \quad (8)$$

This is approximated with a finite number of realizations, $K < \infty$, (9).

$$E[|\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{I_o(u)\}|^2] \approx K^{-1} \sum_{n=1}^K |\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{I_o(u)\}|^2 \quad (9)$$

As the number of realizations, K , increases, the noise power decreases and the resulting average approaches the expected value result. Because each realization is exponentially distributed, averaging K statistically independent realizations of processed speckle data yields a processed image distributed as gamma with K degrees of freedom and the mean equal to the expected value of a single frame [9]. For this reason (and to save processing time), we used an exponential random number generator to produce K statistically independent, noisy object autocorrelations for input to the phase retrieval algorithms. Each exponentially corrupted autocorrelation corresponds to a single realization of observed laser speckle data. Multiple realizations of exponentially noisy autocorrelations were averaged to produce the studied data sets. Other applications may provide different statistics; however, all three algorithms are relevant (and suggested) for this type application. Phillips begins with autocorrelation data as described in this paper's application [3]. Schulz suggests an application where an autocorrelation is produced as in astronomical speckle imaging [2]. Fienup's algorithm has broad implications and is easily extended to this application by operating on the autocorrelation and Power Spectral Density (PSD) pairs. The square root of the observed PSD is the observed modulus, $|F(u)|$, for each iteration. Use of Fienup's algorithm is suggested in this manner by Ref. [4].

3. ALGORITHM REVIEW

This section reviews the mechanics and mathematics of the three algorithms.

Fienup's Iterative Method

Fienup's Error Reduction method is essentially the Gerchberg-Saxton phase retrieval algorithm [1], [10] and is often quoted in literature. Fienup proposes additional algorithm extensions [1]; however, this paper only considers the basic error-reduction method. The algorithm essentially iterates between object and Fourier transform domains where known constraints are applied to the data before continuing with the next iteration. For the object domain, the object is assumed to be positive and within a known observation region, called object support. For the Fourier domain, the modulus of the Fourier Transform of the object field is known from the observed data. For the application considered here, this results from

the square root of the Fourier Transform of the noisy autocorrelation data. Figure 2 depicts a block diagram of Fienup's Error Reduction algorithm [1].

Figure 2. Block Diagram of Fienup's Error Reduction Method

The initial guess for the algorithm can be extremely gross; only the extent of the object need to be known. Therefore, the initial guess can be the support box itself perturbed with random noise. Schulz cautions against using a smooth, uniform image and suggests an asymmetric starting image [2]. This study heeds this suggestion. In a later paper [10], Fienup proposes stopping criteria to be the squared error between the Fourier constraint and the computed Fourier Transform (similar in the object domain for successive iterations). This algorithm is a single frame algorithm; it operates on a single autocorrelation. Without stopping criteria, the algorithm runs until operator intervention or the number of chosen iterations has been exceeded.

Schulz's Recovery Method

Schulz chooses to maximize a log-likelihood of the data where a poisson model is selected (10). Schulz acknowledges that few applications present autocorrelation data corrupted by Poisson noise; however, he states this model does enforce positivity and is similar to cases where the noise is signal dependent. For applications with signal dependent noise but unknown distribution this algorithm may be a good choice. For the application considered in this paper, the autocorrelation does not exhibit Poisson noise; however, this algorithm performs well in low noise conditions and is considered for comparison. Equation (11) depicts the Schulz iterative algorithm using the Poisson model. $\lambda_k(x)$ is the current guess of the object, $\tilde{R}(y)$ is the autocorrelation formed from the measured data, and $R_{\lambda}(y)$ is the autocorrelation formed from the current estimate of the object.

$$L(\lambda) = - \sum_y [R_{\lambda}(y) + \tilde{R}(y) \ln R_{\lambda}(y)] \quad (10)$$

4. ALGORITHM SIMULATION

$$\lambda_{k+1}(x) = \frac{\lambda_k(x)}{\sum \lambda_k(x)} \sum_y [\lambda_k(x+y) + \lambda_k(x-y)] \frac{\tilde{R}(y)}{R_\lambda(y)} \quad (11)$$

The Schulz algorithm also requires a support region where the object is known to exist and an initial guess. The initial guess for the Schulz algorithm can also be a gross starting point, the same as Fienup's. Schulz's algorithm is also a single frame algorithm and no stopping criteria is provided. The Schulz iterative algorithm can be characterized as a gradient search method with object constraints used to aid in convergence. The initial guess (positive with support) enforces a solution only within the support region as well as object positivity.

Phillips' Maximum Likelihood Method

Phillips presents a statistical approach to the phase retrieval problem [3] claiming Gaussian statistics when K is large. While the Central Limit Theorem suggests this is true under the right conditions; the previous discussion and computer simulations suggests this is a poor approximation for our application. Phillips formed his data set in a similar way as this development with the addition of atmospheric turbulence in front of the aperture for his Laser Detection and Ranging (LADAR) scenario. If the data is not normally distributed, Phillips' algorithm will perform at a disadvantage. The statistical approach is extremely powerful; however, this analysis suggests a very large number of realizations are required for the Gaussian assumption to prove true. From the Gaussian assumption, the Log Likelihood is formed in (12).

$$L(o) = -\frac{1}{2\sigma^2(y)} \sum_y \left(d(y) - \sum_x o(x)o(x+y) \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

$o(x)$ is the true object, $d(y)$ is the average speckled autocorrelation, and $\sigma^2(y)$ is the variance. An iterative maximization approach is accomplished with the k th frame data model detailed in (13). Averaging the data over K number of frames is assumed to be Gaussian with a mean equal to the Idell function (3). A sample variance is computed from the K observed frames.

$$d^k(y) = \left| \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left\{ \left| \mathcal{F}^{\lambda z} \{o(x)\} \right|^2 + n^k(u) \right\} \right|^2 \quad (13)$$

Phillips suggests a low-resolution image as the starting point. In Ref. [11], Phillips describes a joint algorithm using both pupil and image plane data to aid image recovery. However, this study used only a random image as the starting point and found the algorithm to converge. The Phillips algorithm may be implemented as a multi-frame algorithm (iteratively operating on each realization), although this was not considered for this study. Lastly, Phillips suggests a statistical based stopping criteria; however, this was not implemented in this study.

All three algorithms were implemented as single data frame operations; only operating on a single autocorrelation as the observed data. The data input for the algorithms were generated from the average of K realizations of noisy autocorrelations corrupted with exponential noise (see Fig. 3). K represents the number of processed laser speckle realizations averaged to produce the autocorrelation input for the algorithms. As K increases, the closer the noisy autocorrelation approaches the true autocorrelation and lower the noise power (8). With $K = 1$, the noise power is extremely high and the algorithms are expected to perform poorly. Phillips' algorithm can not operate on a single laser speckle as a sample variance must be computed from multiple realizations of laser speckle.

Figure 3. Method for Generating Algorithm Input

For the simulation, we repeated each phase retrieval algorithm operation 50 times with 50 different starting images (or initial guesses) and averaged the resulting error computation. As described by Schulz in [2], an asymmetric starting image should be chosen where, within the support region, the image pixels are independent random variables distributed uniformly over the interval $[0.99, 1.01]$ and exactly zero outside the region of support. This simulation executed this suggestion for generating random and independent starting images. This minimized the *a priori* knowledge of the target to only the support region and positivity. Two target cases were considered for this study to highlight algorithm performance: (1) the target field going to zero within the support region and (2) the target field not going to zero within the support region. Figure 4 demonstrates the two target cases. Case 1, is three simple bars of varying strength with the background behind the bars exactly zero and uniform illumination. This is not completely unrealistic as space-borne targets correspond to this type of target. The support region for Case 1 is twice the extent of the bars. Case 2 is three simple bars of varying strength that extend the width of the support region on a uniform, non-zero background. The target field is illuminated by a circular, laser beam with a gaussian roll-off. The support region for Case 2 is simulated to be the circular laser beam footprint. Case 2, although not entirely realistic, corresponds to a target field on the earth observed by an airborne or space-borne sensor. Figure 5 depicts the true target autocorrelations and a single noisy autocorrelation corrupted with exponential noise. Figure 6 depicts the average of 100 autocorrelations corrupted with exponential noise. The more realizations averaged, the closer the resulting data set approaches the true autocorrelation. This produces a higher signal to noise ratio but requires increased dwell time on target.

Figure 4. [A] Target Case 1, [B] Target Case 2

Figure 5. [A,C]: Target 1 True and Noisy Autocorrelations; [B,D]: Target 2 True and Noisy Autocorrelations

Figure 6. Average of 100 noisy autocorrelations [A] Target 1, [B] Target 2

5. RESULTS

The results of the simulation are presented here for algorithm comparison. These results are not exhaustive; however, this brief study does highlight general algorithm performance. Figures 7 and 8 demonstrate the performance of the three algorithms for Target Case 1. Figure 7 depicts MSE and correlation coefficient vs number of realizations (noise power) for 1000 iterations. Figure 8 shows the MSE and correlation coefficient vs iterations for 500 realizations. As shown in Figure 8, Schulz's algorithm did incrementally diverge or oscillate as iterations increased. In most cases, the best object estimate occurred with very few iterations. This is believed to be due to the search nature of the algorithm coupled with

the incorrect noise distribution. The noise causes the algorithm to oscillate with increased iterations. Even with the wrong noise distribution, Schulz's algorithm performed well as compared to the other two algorithms. Similarly, Phillips' algorithm also showed minor oscillation with increasing iterations. This is also believed to be due to noise sensitivity. Fienup's algorithm performed as previously documented; it incrementally approaches the true object with increased iterations. As expected, all algorithms improve with increased realizations of speckled autocorrelations. Figures 9 - 11 provide example recovered images for each algorithm for 2000 realizations and 1000 iterations.

Figure 7. MSE [A] and ρ [B] for Three Algorithms vs Number of Realizations, 1000 Iterations, Target 1

Figure 8. MSE [A] and ρ [B] for Three Algorithms vs Iterations, 500 Realizations, Target 1

Figures 12 - 14 demonstrate the performance of the three algorithms for Target Case 2. Fienup's algorithm did not converge for this case. The algorithm stagnated as described in [12]. Figure 12 depicts MSE and correlation coefficient vs number of realizations (noise power) for 1000 iterations. Figure 13 shows the MSE and Correlation Coefficient vs Iterations for 500 realizations. Figure 14 provides example recovered images for 500 realizations and 1000 iterations.

6. CONCLUSIONS

For the scenarios considered in this study, Schulz's algorithm demonstrates the best ability to overcome noise. However, Schulz's algorithm may tend to diverge or oscillate as iter-

Figure 9. Schulz Example Image; Target 1, 2000 Realizations, 1000 Iterations

Figure 10. Fienup Example Image; Target 1, 2000 Realizations, 1000 Iterations

Figure 11. Phillips Example Image; Target 1, 2000 Realizations, 1000 Iterations

ations increase. Large numbers of iterations do not incrementally improve performance. Fienup’s algorithm provides a robust method that, except for stagnant cases, converges toward the solution with increased iterations. Phillips’ algorithm performs well under the conditions presented here and demonstrates good performance when the target is complex and the number of realizations is large. For this application, noisy autocorrelation data with exponential statistics, Schulz’s algorithm is the best choice of the three reviewed algorithms. Phillips’ algorithm performs similar to Schulz’s for complex targets with non-zero backgrounds. The author proposes a new phase retrieval algorithm be developed based on the exponential distribution found with the processed data. A Maximum Likelihood Estimator using the Exponential model should outperform these reviewed algorithms for this application. This will be explored in future research.

Figure 12. MSE [A] and ρ [B] for Two Algorithms vs Number of Realizations, 1000 Iterations, Target 2

Figure 13. MSE [A] and ρ [B] for Two Algorithms vs Iterations, 500 Realizations, Target 2

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Figure 14. Target 2 Example Recovered images, 500 Realizations, 1000 Iterations; [A] Schulz, [B] Phillips, [C] Original

BIOGRAPHY

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